

Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction Part II Dynamic Probability

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In Part I we considered light moving in the positive x direction striking a medium with a different index of refraction with some reflecting and the rest refracting. We argued one may immediately write a conservation of energy equation, but this is a single equation while there are two unknowns, the intensity of the reflected beam and the refracted, assuming the incident intensity is known. (We also argued that one also has the relation $E=pc$ for a photon, but this is not needed to solve for the two intensities.) Our main point was that instead of seeking another independent equation (containing new information), one may write the conservation of energy equation as a product of two equations $A + B = C$ ((1a)) and $A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2$ ((1b)) where $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ is the energy conservation equation. Thus energy conservation contains all of the information needed, but one must move to a square root of probability picture in order to obtain the two equations needed to solve for the reflected and refracted values B,C and then the intensities BB and CC.

In Part I, we noted that the reflection/refraction problem may be presented as a steady state one in which the scenario is not changing in time. A Maxwell-Boltzmann gas in equilibrium also does not change in time, but here there is a difference, namely a lack of time reversal invariance. In other words there is a distinct direction of motion i.e. the incident and refracted beams move in the positive direction only and the reflected in the negative x. The problem, however, is also a probabilistic one because given a single photon, it either reflects or refracts with certain probabilities. Thus we suggest there exists in this physical steady state problem a dynamic or directional probability. This probability is related to space and may be positive or negative unlike the usual time probabilities linked to events i.e. classical probability theory. The conservation of energy equation is a classical probability one, but dynamic motion probabilities are present in the problem and should also be manifest in equations. In fact the two dynamic probability equations allow for the solving of the reflected/refracted intensities (probabilities), but are also directly linked to the conservation of energy equation which may be written as: $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ which points towards flow in two different directions. Thus we argue that a dynamic directional probability is responsible for the decomposition of the energy conservation equation into two dynamic probability ones.

Conservation of Energy in a Reflection/Refraction Problem

Consider an incident light beam (A) traveling in the positive x direction hitting a medium with a different index of refraction (and light speed c_2). Part reflects B and part refracts C according to two probability values, but energy is conserved overall. Thus one may immediately write a conservation of energy equation (grouped in time) i.e. with the incident beam on one side and the reflected and refracted on the other:

$$I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

where $I(A)$ is intensity. A traditional way to obtain ((1)) is to consider the continuity of a photon's electric field constant $\times \exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative at $x=0$ as done in (1). Thus $A\exp(ip1)$, $B\exp(-ip1x)$ and $C\exp(ip2x)$ represent the three beams. In Part I, we argued that one may find the result simply by starting with the conservation of energy equation ((1)) and breaking it into two equations using a difference of squares. To do so, one changes the time grouping into a space one i.e.

$$I(A)/c_1 - I(B)/c_1 = I(C)/c_2 \quad ((2))$$

Here the two beams in the same medium (space) with the same c_1 are grouped together, but a minus sign appears indicating a change in flow direction. We note that in ((2)) $I(A), I(B)$ and $I(C)$ are necessarily positive values. ((2)) is a single equation and does not suffice to solve for $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ given $I(A)$. In Part I we argued that one may consider the LHS of ((2)) as similar to a difference of squares and write:

$$A + B = C \quad \text{with } I(A)=AA, I(B)=BB \text{ and } I(C)=CC \quad \text{and } A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2 \quad ((3))$$

Thus one solves for B and C and also has energy conservation ((2)) because this was the starting point.

((3)) is in the form of a kind of OR probability scenario, but with square root type probabilities A, B, C i.e. quantum wavefunction type probabilities. This new probability scheme groups probabilities by space, not time as A and B are on the same side in the equation.

Solving ((3)) leads to results given in (1) namely:

$$B/A = (c_2 - c_1) / (c_2 + c_1) \quad \text{and} \quad C/A = 2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((4))$$

One may note that if $c_2 < c_1$ then B is a negative probability.

((3)) allows one to solve for B and C and ultimately the reflected and refracted intensities, but one may ask: What is the physical reason for these two equations?

Dynamic Directional-Probability

In classical probability theory one has positive probabilities with values between and including 0 and 1 which add to 1. Above, a probability scheme arises which allows for negative probability values, represents flow and probability and also represents square root values of the usual classical probabilities i.e. $I(A)=AA, I(B)=BB$ and $I(C)=CC$.

To try to account for this, we notice that the steady state scenario (i.e. one which removes time) of an incident beam moving in the positive x direction and then reflecting and refracting still contains flow in time information. For instance the incident and refracted beams move in the positive direction while the reflected moves in the negative. Thus it is not enough to know the probabilities BB and CC , one must also know directions which are linked to flow (otherwise there would be no directions). One may also note that the problem does not have time reversal symmetry.

A conservation of energy equation accounts for time differences i.e. the energy of the incident beam is equated to that of the reflected and refracted, but it does not include flow. One may write it in the form ((2)) to see a negative sign appear associated with reflection, but this is not an a priori space grouped probability equation if it explicitly contains a negative sign.

We suggest the existence of a dynamic directional-probability which explicitly describes flow and its direction as well as probability in a steady state problem. We suggest that time is removed in the steady state problem and that one should consider an OR situation grouping in space. Then one may write a priori:

$$A+B = C \quad (A \text{ and } B \text{ are grouped together in space}) \quad ((5))$$

Next we consider, using $E=pc$ with E constant a momentum conservation equation using this new probability:

$$Ap_1 - Bp_1 = Cp_2 \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{or} \quad AE/c_1 - BE/c_1 = CE/c_2 \quad ((6b)) \rightarrow A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2 \quad ((6c))$$

Equations ((6)) allow one to solve for B and C and show that B may be negative. Thus ((6b)) which has the appearance of a conservation of energy equation if one brings the term $-BE/c_1$ to the RHS cannot be one because B may be negative. It is, however, the idea of a difference of squares which ensures that the form of ((6b)) remains unchanged except for $A \rightarrow AA$, $B \rightarrow BB$ and $C \rightarrow CC$ which then may describe energy conservation and classical probabilities i.e. AA etc.

Thus we suggest that there are actually two kinds of probabilities in this problem in a very similar manner in which there exists a wavefunction $W(x)$ and a spatial classical probability $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ in the quantum mechanics of particles with a rest mass.

Conclusion

In Part I we considered a beam of light A traveling in the positive x direction and reflecting B and refracting C at $x=0$. We wrote a conservation of energy equation: $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$ with $I(A)$, $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ necessarily being positive. We then wrote $I(A)/c_1 - I(B)/c_1 = I(C)/c_2$ and argued that if $I(A)=AA$, $I(B)=BB$ and $I(C)=CC$, this is equivalent to two equations: $A+B = C$ and $A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2$. These two are needed to solve for B and C in terms of A and automatically guarantee energy conservation.

In this note we try to account for the physical reason that such a square root probability i.e. A, B, C exists in the first place. We argue that even though one has a steady state problem in which time is removed, there is still flow with a direction. We suggest the existence of dynamic flow probability which may be positive or negative and should be grouped in space not time. We consider an OR situation i.e. addition for the probability and the average momentum:

$$A+B=C \quad \text{and} \quad A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2$$

The second equation has the same form as an energy conservation equation if one uses $E=pc$ with E being the same in all cases. The problem is that B may be negative. Thus the two above equations allow for one to solve for B and C in terms of A , but the second equation is not a

conservation of energy equation even though it has the correct form. This form may be kept intact and A,B,C converted to AA,BB,CC >0 by multiplying by A+B and C i.e. using differences of squares. This then becomes the conservation of energy equation.

Thus we suggest the existence of a dynamic directional-probability which groups in space and may take on positive or negative values, but maps to the usual classical probability i.e. is the square root of such a probability.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change